

ELEPHANT

IN THE LAB

SHORT ANALYSIS

Doctor coauthor

Short title	Doctor coauthor
Long title	The 20 highest performing authors in Medicine published more than 7700 articles in seven years.
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Date published	10 July 2017
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.815926
Cite as (APA)	Schmidt, M., Fecher, B., Kobsda, C. (2017). The 20 highest performing authors in Medicine published more than 7700 articles in six years. <i>Elephant in the lab</i> . DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.815926

Description

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Medicine* is 11 on average with a maximum of 1193 authors (Figure 1). Only *Physics and Astronomy* (Schmidt et al. [2017a](#)) as well as *Biochemistry, Genetics, and Molecular Biology* (Schmidt et al. [2017a](#)) have higher numbers regarding authors per article. The mean number of coauthors is increasing by 0.4 per year in the

respective time period. With a number of $n = 7741$ articles in seven years, *Medicine* is the subject area with the most publications according to our methodology (see below). The articles in this analysis were cited 30.7 times on average and with a maximum of 2861 citations.

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA MEDICINE

Increase of co-authors per year = 0.4
Number of articles = 7741

Figure 1: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Medicine*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. Due to a limitation of the y-axis, some outliers are not shown. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

Methodology

The results of the Advanced search in Scopus were restricted by an algorithm with

- a time period of publishing (2010 to 2016)
- the document types (articles or reviews),
- and a quantitative limitation regarding the publication output (articles by the 20 highest performing authors with the most Scopus listed articles in every subject area).

For details and code see Schmidt et al. [2017b](#).

References

Schmidt, M., Fecher, B., Kobsda, C. (2017a). How many authors does it really need to write a paper? [Elephant in the lab](#). [Link](#).

Schmidt, M., Fecher, B., Kobsda, C. (2017b). Methodology for the analysis of authors using meta data from Scopus. [Elephant in the lab](#). [Link](#).